

Relevance and Challenges of Implementing Entrepreneurship Curriculum for Skill Acquisition in Primary School

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13825629>

Abstract

This study examined the relevance and challenges of implementing entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition in primary schools in southwestern Nigeria. The study raised two research questions and formulated two hypotheses. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, the population of the study was 37339 stakeholders made up of primary school teachers and education secretaries in Lagos, Oyo, and Osun in southwestern Nigeria. A structured questionnaire titled “Implementation of Entrepreneurship Studies for Skill Acquisition by primary school pupils (IESESAPASPQ) was used to gather the data. The instrument went through face and content validation by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was ensured using the Cronbach Alpha reliability method and the result yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.92. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data collected to answer research questions. Hypotheses were tested using independent samples t-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), at a 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary school will be relevant to pupils' acquisition of skills, and lead to the accomplishment of sustainable development goals (mean=3.30 SD=0.80), There was no significant difference between the mean responses of primary school teachers and education secretaries regarding the relevance of implementing entrepreneurship studies in basic school for skill acquisition by primary school pupils ($t_{441}=1.830$, $p>0.05$), there was no significant difference in the mean response of primary school teachers and education secretaries regarding the challenges of implementing entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition by primary school pupils. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that entrepreneurship studies is relevant to primary school curriculum. It was recommended among others that the government and stakeholders should ensure that entrepreneurship studies are implemented at the primary school level.

Keywords: Challenges, Entrepreneurship, Curriculum, Skill Acquisition, Primary School

Introduction

Nigeria is presently experiencing economic difficulties. This is reflected in the extent of unemployment in Nigeria, particularly among the younger generation. A significant number of individuals are wandering the streets in pursuit of elusive jobs without any prospect of survival. The escalating unemployment rate among Nigerians in recent years has caused significant apprehension and profound distress in society. The creation of a pool of creative, highly educated, and business-minded people within the nation can aid in overcoming the challenges of

unemployment. Such an outcome can only be attained through effective management of the country's socio-economic and political conditions, which would serve to motivate and inspire its citizens. This is crucial, as a thriving economy necessitates a larger pool of ambitious and capable young individuals who are inclined to pursue entrepreneurship.

The myriad of challenges facing Nigeria as a nation can be ascribed to the elevated rates of unemployment and abject poverty among its populace. As the adage goes, "An idle hand is the devil's workshop." According to Ademiluyi, Ayanwole, and Aluko (2022), Boko Haram terrorists and banditry provide a substantial obstacle in the north-east and north-west regions, specifically in Borno, Yobe, Adamawa, and Kaduna States. Moreover, the north-central and southwest regions, particularly Benue, Niger, Oyo, and Ogun states, are currently facing detrimental conflicts between herders and farmers, along with widespread incidents of kidnapping. The activities of militant groups, pipeline saboteurs, and separatist instigators in the south-south and south-east areas are continually undermining the development and progress of the country, especially in Delta, Rivers, Bayelsa, and Imo States. Sustainably addressing these difficulties necessitates the implementation of strategies that encompass short-term, medium-term, and long-term perspectives. The short-term strategy involves providing sustenance to the most susceptible individuals, while the medium-term strategy focuses on generating job prospects for the population and establishing a favourable atmosphere for potential investors and employers. Nevertheless, the long-term strategy involves altering behaviour and cultivating a mindset that focuses on developing programs to educate individuals about the practical and sustainable path to becoming entrepreneurs, employers, and self-sufficient members of society (Ademiluyi, Ayanwole & Aluko, 2022).

Ajagbe (2014) regarded entrepreneurship studies as a means of equipping learners with the necessary information, abilities, and incentives to thrive in entrepreneurial endeavours across different contexts. Hence, it is undeniably a crucial facet of continuous education. This study aimed at providing learners with the necessary capabilities to think creatively, objectively and analyze business ideas, solve problems successfully, and make optimal contributions to society, regardless of their age, gender, or ethnicity. As stated by Bubou and Okrigwe (2011), a benefit of studying entrepreneurship is that it helps cultivate students' confidence to start their businesses, by teaching them different strategies for seizing opportunities.

Studying entrepreneurship equips students with the knowledge, skills, and motivation to be talented and effectively engage in successful entrepreneurship across many settings (Ajagbe, 2014). The talents encompass the effective utilization of concepts, data, and facts to facilitate the growth of skills, services, or the successful placement of learners in businesses. As per Maryrose and Obiajulu (2020), entrepreneurship education offers individuals increased prospects to express their creative autonomy, enhance self-confidence, and have a heightened sense of personal agency. It also helps users gain entrepreneurial skills for efficient and productive living. Entrepreneurs possess the ability to shape, actualize, and realize a nation's economic ambitions, therefore exerting significant influence over its destiny. Therefore, it is crucial to incorporate entrepreneurial skills into the fundamental curriculum of elementary schools, to foster early awareness.

The primary school level in Nigeria, as stated by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014), aims to achieve the following objectives in basic education: fostering a lifelong passion for reading, writing, and effective communication in children; establishing a strong basis for critical and scientific thinking; imparting citizenship education to enable children to actively participate in and contribute to society; shaping the character of children and instilling in them a strong sense of morality; offering opportunities for children to develop practical skills that will enable them to

function effectively within their capacity in society; and providing children with the necessary foundations for further educational progress, including vocational training specific to their local area.

Starting from the primary school level, it would be advantageous to provide pupils with practical and pertinent entrepreneurial skills. These include adaptable thinking skills, which allow them to adjust to societal changes; collaborative skills, which enable them to work effectively with their peers both in and outside of school; innovative skills, which foster the discovery of new ideas and innovations; and creativity skills, which cultivate a mindset for generating novel creations. This is due to the worldwide unemployment crisis, which necessitates a greater focus on the quality and substance of training provided to learners, particularly in the area of skill acquisition (Ademiluyi, 2021). However, despite the significance of entrepreneurship studies and the inclusion of the subject in the curriculum by NERDC in 2013, it has not been incorporated into the primary school curriculum in Nigeria, and in the southwestern regions. Young children have been denied the chance to acquire the necessary resources for workforce preparation in trade and commerce, as well as the advancement of their entrepreneurial studies, as stated in the National Policy on Education of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014). This might be attributed to the postponed implementation of entrepreneurship studies, which presents difficulty in achieving the objectives set by the policy in this area (Sofoluwe, Shokunbi, Raimi, & Ajewole, 2013).

The lack of curriculum implementation may be linked to the difficulties encountered in achieving effective curriculum implementation. According to Abakpa and Agbo-Egwu (2013), Nigerian elementary schools lack the necessary structures and activities to effectively apply the curriculum. Charity (2015) identifies many primary barriers to basic education in Nigeria. These include a lack of adequate resources for specialized teachers, substandard quality and training of teachers, a paucity of relevant instructional materials, and inadequate supervision and guidance for educators. To introduce entrepreneurship studies at the elementary level of education, it is necessary to identify and address the issues that may impede its successful implementation.

To accelerate the implementation of entrepreneurship studies at the primary school level, it is crucial for the government and other respondents to fully grasp the relevance of introducing this subject as well as the challenges that could confront its implementation. Presently, there is a dearth of empirical research studies in southwest Nigeria that investigate the essential variables that need to be considered before implementing entrepreneurship studies at the primary school level. The lack of research has resulted in a knowledge deficit. This study addressed this knowledge deficit by examining the relevance and challenges of implementing entrepreneurship studies for skills acquisition by primary school pupils.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relevance of implementing entrepreneurship studies for basic skill acquisition by primary school pupils?
2. What are the challenges of implementing entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition among primary school pupils?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean responses of primary school teachers and Education secretaries regarding the relevance of implementing entrepreneurship curriculum for basic skill acquisition by primary school pupils.
- H₀₂ There is no significant difference in the mean responses of respondents regarding the challenges of implementing entrepreneurship curriculum for skill acquisition among primary school pupils based on their years of experience.

Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study consists of 37,339 respondents made up of 37,256 primary school teachers and 83 Education secretaries in Lagos, Oyo, and Osun States, in Southwestern, Nigeria. All the 83 Education Secretaries were purposefully selected due to their small and manageable size while a research advisor was used to select 384 teachers from the entire population of teachers at a 0.05 margin of error. The instrument for collecting data was a structured questionnaire, titled “Implementation of Entrepreneurship Curriculum for Skill Acquisition by Primary School Pupil’s Questionnaire (IECF SAPSPQ), which consisted of 20 items in line with the variables of the study. The questionnaire was placed on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The questionnaire draft underwent face and content validity assessment by three experts. Cronbach’s Alpha method of reliability was employed to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument which was found to be 0.92. This shows that the instrument is highly reliable and stable. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. Independent samples t-test was considered appropriate for testing the null hypothesis one because of its ability to compare two groups of independent variables while One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test hypothesis two at a 0.05 level of significance. For the research questions, mean scores between 3.25 – 4.00, 2.50 – 3.24, 1.75 – 2.49, and 1.00 – 1.74 were categorized as Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Disagreed, and Strongly Disagreed respectively. Similarly, for the null hypotheses testing, if the observed significant value for ANOVA as well as t-test is equal to or less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected, otherwise, the null hypothesis was retained.

Results

Research Question One: What is the relevance of implementing entrepreneurship studies for basic skill acquisition by primary school pupils?

Table 1: Mean rating of the Respondents on the relevance of entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition

S/N	Item Statements	Mean	Std	Remarks
1	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will lead to the accomplishment of Sustainable Development Goals in Basic Education.	3.50	0.66	Strongly Agree
2	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will lead to the accomplishment of children's right to comprehensive functional education.	3.21	0.69	Agree
3	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will lead to the formation of a positive attitude towards entrepreneurship among primary school pupils.	3.32	0.78	Strongly Agree
4	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will promote innovative ideas among primary school pupils.	3.26	0.82	Strongly Agree
5	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will enhance the skills of primary school pupils in buying and selling.	3.31	0.81	Strongly Agree
6	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will instil creativity skills in pupils right from their youth.	3.33	0.75	Strongly Agree
7	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will lead to the acquisition of initiative skills in the pupils.	3.27	0.71	Strongly Agree
8	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will lead to the acquisition of entrepreneurship skills by the pupils.	3.26	0.86	Strongly Agree
9	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will promote the acquisition of business competency skills among the pupils.	3.28	0.75	Strongly Agree
10	Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will enhance the acquisition of basic computer skills.	3.23	0.76	Agree
	Weighted Mean	3.30	0.80	Strongly Agree

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 reveals that respondents strongly agreed that Implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will lead to the accomplishment of Sustainable Development Goals on Basic Education (Mean = 3.50), they also agreed that; implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will lead to the accomplishment of children's right to comprehensive functional education (Mean = 3.21), implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary school will lead to the formation of positive attitude towards entrepreneurship among primary school pupils (Mean = 3.32).

Equally, respondents agreed that implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will promote innovative ideas among primary school pupils (Mean = 3.26), implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will enhance the skills of primary school pupils in buying and selling (Mean = 3.31), implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will instil creativity skills in pupils right from their youth (Mean = 3.33), implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will lead to the acquisition of initiative skills in the pupils (Mean = 3.27), implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will lead to the acquisition of entrepreneurship skills by the pupils (Mean = 3.26), implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will promote the acquisition of business competency skills among the pupils and that implementing entrepreneurship studies in primary schools will enhance acquisition of basic computer skills (Mean = 3.28 and 3.23). The standard deviations of the items are low ranging from 0.66 to 0.86 indicating that their responses are not too widespread. In summary, respondents agreed that entrepreneurship studies are relevant to primary school curricula with a grand weighted mean and standard deviation of (=3.30; SD = 0.80).

Research Question Two: What are the possible challenges of implementing entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition among primary school pupils?

Table 2: Mean ratings of Respondents on possible challenges of implementing entrepreneurship curriculum for skill acquisition

S/N	Item Statements	Mean	Std	Remarks
1	Non-provision of specialized teachers to teach different aspects of entrepreneurship studies in primary school will make it impossible. to achieve the objective of the subject at the basic school level.	3.40	0.77	Strongly Agree
2	The high teacher-to-pupil ratio is a serious challenge to the effective implementation of entrepreneurship studies at the primary school level.	2.98	0.80	Agree
3	Non-involvement of primary school teachers in curriculum development will affect the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in primary schools.	3.30	0.68	Strongly Agree
4	Frequent changes in government policies and directives about teaching and learning at the primary school level are a hindrance to the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in primary schools.	3.40	0.74	Strongly Agree
5	Inadequate instructional materials will hinder the effective acquisition of skills in entrepreneurship among primary school pupils.	3.67	0.67	Strongly Agree
6	Shortage of funding will affect the effective teaching and learning of entrepreneurship studies.	3.33	0.75	Strongly Agree
7	Inadequate specialized workshops for teaching and learning entrepreneurship studies will make the achievement of entrepreneurship studies objectives at the primary school level difficult.	3.31	0.78	Strongly Agree

8	Shortage of furniture for both teachers and pupils will make teaching and learning of entrepreneurship studies difficult.	3.28	0.78	Strongly Agree
9	Non-provision of a stable power supply will affect the acquisition of skills in some areas where water is needed.	3.23	0.79	Agree
10	Inadequate on-the-job training for teachers to enhance their pedagogical skills will not allow them to understand current and modern teaching skills needed to effectively implement entrepreneurship studies	3.27	0.76	Strongly Agree
	Weighted Mean	3.32	0.75	Strongly Agree

Source; Field Survey, 2023

Analysis in Table 2 reveals that the respondents agreed that challenges confronting the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in primary school among others include; non-provision of specialized teachers to teach different aspect of entrepreneurship studies in primary school will make it impossible to achieve the objective of the subject at the basic school level (mean = 3.40), high teacher to pupils' ratio is a serious challenge against effective implementation of entrepreneurship studies at the primary school level (mean = 2.98), non-involvement of primary school teachers in curriculum development will affect the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in primary schools (mean = 3.30), frequent changes in government policies and directives in relation teaching and learning at the primary school level is a hindrance to the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in primary schools (mean = 3.40), inadequate instructional materials will hinder effective acquisition of skills on entrepreneurship among primary school pupils (mean = 3.67). Respondents equally, agreed that; a shortage of funding will affect the effective teaching and learning of entrepreneurship studies (mean = 3.33), inadequate specialized workshops for teaching and learning of entrepreneurship studies will achieve entrepreneurship studies objectives at the primary school level difficult (mean = 3.31), shortage of furniture for both teachers and the pupils will make teaching and learning of entrepreneurship studies inconducive and that; non-provision of stable power supply will affect the acquisition of skills in some area where water is needed (mean = 3.28 and 3.23), also, inadequate on-the-job training for teachers to enhance their pedagogical skills will not allow them to understand current and modern teaching skills needed to effectively implement entrepreneurship studies (mean = 3.27). In summary, respondents agreed that all the items listed above are some of the challenges impeding the implementation of entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition by primary school pupils, with a grand weighted mean and standard deviation of (= 3.32; SD = 0.75).

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of primary school teachers and Education secretaries regarding the relevance of implementing entrepreneurship studies for basic skill acquisition by primary school pupils.

Table 3: Summary of t-test of the relevance of implementing entrepreneurship studies for basic skill acquisition by primary school pupils

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	Df	p-value	Decision
Primary school teachers	319	3.30	0.26	1.830	441	0.177	H₀1 Not Rejected
Education secretaries	83	3.13	0.66				

Source: Field survey, 2023 P>0.05

The data in Table 3 reveals that the respondents' responses showed they agreed that entrepreneurship studies are relevant to the primary school curriculum with a grand weighted mean and standard deviation of (= 3.30; SD = 0.80). Their responses are close to the mean as the standard deviation is low. The table also revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of primary school teachers and Education Secretaries regarding the relevance of implementing entrepreneurship studies for basic skill acquisition by primary school pupils (t 441 = 1.830, P>0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of primary school teachers and education secretaries regarding the relevance of implementing entrepreneurship studies for basic skill acquisition by primary school pupils was not rejected.

H₀2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of respondents on the challenges of implementing entrepreneurship curriculum for skill acquisition among primary school pupils based on their years of experience.

Table 4: Summary of ANOVA on challenges of implementing entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition among primary school pupils

Group	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F	Sig	Decision
21 years +	2.185	4	0.550	2.064	0.090	H₀ 6 Not Rejected
16-20 years						
11-15 years	115.924	438	0.270			
6-10 years						
1-5 years						
Total	118.109	442				

Source: Field survey, 2023 P>0.05

The data in Table 4 reveals that respondents agreed inadequate instructional materials and inadequate specialized workshops for teaching and learning among others will constitute challenges in the implementation of entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition by primary school pupils (mean =3.32; SD = 0.75). The result of the analysis of variance as presented in Table 4 reveals that the calculated value of [F (4, 438) = 2.064] and the observed probability value is 0.090 which is less than the fixed probability value of 0.05 (P < 0.05). This indicated that the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of

respondents on the challenges of implementing entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition among primary school pupils based on their years of experience was not rejected.

Discussion

The findings revealed respondents agreed that entrepreneurship studies are highly relevant to primary school curricula. This implies that implementing entrepreneurship studies is relevant for basic skill acquisition by primary school pupils. This finding affirmed the assertion made by Elindra and Sarah (2017) that entrepreneurship education can augment early childhood creativity. This finding also corroborates the revelation of María, María, Lorena, and Elvia (2017) argue that exposing elementary school children to entrepreneurship studies has several benefits. These include gaining administrative knowledge and entrepreneurial abilities, as well as reinforcing business ideals.

Furthermore, the finding on the challenges of implementing entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition among primary school pupils indicates that respondents unanimously acknowledged that all the items listed in the questionnaire are obstacles that hinder the implementation of entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition by primary school pupils. The results also indicated that respondents' reactions to the challenges of conducting entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition among elementary school kids do not vary based on their years of experience. This finding corroborates the revelation of Harriet, Gladwell, and Maureen (2021) that implementation of a competency-based curriculum is greatly challenged by a lack of adequate learning facilities, lack of adequate training of teachers on how to implement the curriculum, large class sizes, lack of adequate teachers, lack of adequate teaching-learning materials, ignorance and lack of cooperation from parents. More so, primary school teachers in public schools faced a lot of challenges that hindered the effective implementation of the curriculum. Similarly, Musibau, Amanda, Saadat, and Nkam (2016) in line with this finding also revealed that the problems faced in teaching entrepreneurship education at the upper basic school level include lack of equipment and ample spaces for disseminating lectures, lack of concentration of learners due to orientation, not having satisfactory material and funding, very limited time allotted on timetable, lack of enough workshop.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it could be deduced that entrepreneurship studies are relevant to primary school curriculum, and problem-solving. Furthermore, inadequate instructional materials and inadequate specialized workshops for teaching and learning among others will constitute challenges in the implementation of entrepreneurship studies for skill acquisition by primary school pupils. The study implies that if entrepreneurship studies are not effectively implemented at the primary school level, the challenges of rising unemployment which has become a worrisome issue may not be permanently overcome soon.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The teaching of entrepreneurship studies at the primary school level would promote the acquisition of basic skills among primary school pupils. Therefore, the government at various levels and other respondents should ensure that entrepreneurship studies are implemented at the primary school level.

2. Governments at all levels needed to provide adequate funding for the implementation. This could be in the form of employing more vocational teachers to teach the subject and provision of adequate and relevant facilities, equipment provision as well as instructional materials.

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